

Awareness Program on Knowledge and Attitude on Mental Health and Mental Illness Among School in Selected Area

Knowledge and Attitude Regarding Psychiatric Health and Illness

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Abstract:- Study on awareness Regarding psychiatric health and Mental illness among school Candidates on their knowledge and attitude regarding Psychiatric illness among adolescences students high school in selected area .Frequency and percentage to be computed for describing the sample characteristics. The knowledge score of degree college students in total content area be computed. The Practice score of Coefficient of correlation to be computed to determine the relationship between intelligence and Attitude Chi-square test to Identify the association of awareness with selected variables.

I. INTRODUCTION

People are taking mental illness very lightly there are many areas in the world where people Treating mental disorder with their own tradition knowledge and perspective

Attitudes towards people with mental Problems dates back to the historic era, they people believed the person who Is having mental it ‘possessed by spirits , devil or Ghost ’. People diagnosed with mental illnesses have different way to think and treat and make some changes in public perception from those hospitalized for ‘physical’ conditions such as cancer or Physical disease like arthritis , diabetes etc. we clearly observed mentally ill people not only acted differently looked different. also

They are not aware About organization and institution where the disease has been treated So we start from the upbringing generation from the right place which is school

So we start to target some schools from high school students of higher secondary schools

II. DETAIL REVIEW

Mental disease affects many population around the world, mental disorder unlike other chronic physical conditions like heart disease and hypertrophy, is associated with a number of misleading and myths. For instance, it is very normal for people to imagine that mental disorder is caused by social and moral weakness and or is in the

possession of unwanted spirit and ghost The age group between 17-23 is a vital time in a human’s life. These period is the time where growth and development is on peak specially mentally growth we observe in some cases in the population where some people Enroll in studies, job and other activities and departments .

➤ *Clinical Manifestation*

- Feeling anxious or worried We get worried or stressed because of different situation and problems . But fear could be the clinical manifestation of a mental health illness if worry and anxiety is constant ging like this inside the person this interferes a person all the time which include Other symptoms of anxiety `and tachycardia, shortness of breath, sweating, , feeling dizzy and restlessness, diarrhoea .
- Feeling depressed or unhappy -Clinical manifestation of depression and stress include a person feeling sad or irritation for the few weeks or more and having lack of motivation and activity , lose interest in a hobbies or isolated all the time.
- Emotional outbursts -People has a different level of moods and emotion , but sometimes a dramatic or suddenly changes in mood, like extreme stress or anger, can be a sign and symptom of mental disorder.
- Sleep problems -changes in person’s sleeping habit could be a clinical sign and symptoms of a mental health illness. For example lack of sleep know as insomnia could be a signal of anxiety or substance abuse. Too much Sleeping or too little could indicate sleeping disorder

➤ *Etiology*

For instance various factors could show result in a duration of poor mental health status

- Enviroment
- Past History
- Occupation
- Social life
- Family enviroment
- Past Psychiatric details

- Peers groups
- Interpersonal relationships
- substance use
- Genetic Factor

➤ *Classification*

We just go through a flowing type of disorders which will be only treated by Medical intervention and care in special organization which is totally different from common hospitals

- Personality
- Somatoform
- Delirium
- Dementia
- Phobic Anxiety
- Substance use
- Schizophrenia
- Anorexia Nervosa
- Bulimia Nervosa

➤ *Why Mental Health Matter in Schools ?*

Mental health Awareness needs in Higher secondary School shows in Fig 1 is Crucial Important because youth and children’s we have a diagnostic Emotional, Behavioral health disease conditions in youth and have a problems and challenges that is chronic to make barrier. According to Data collection showed that mentally sickness harm so many kids and higher school children’s aged between 6-18 at least and many approx. More than 80% do not receive the mental health care and treatment properly .

We can able to deal the things and recognize it for support kids and their thinking in Schools .Brain disorder are mostly seen and visualize during children and adult. If we detect in beginning chances of curable is Probably high because Primary detected and intervention work.

Fig1 High School

➤ *Our Goals*

- To identify that Students are aware or not .
- To Minimize the life critical risk .
- To Maximize the Mind Growth and development .
- To find the Barrier and Problems.
- To promote logical and critical thinking
- To promote and facts regarding Treatment
- To reduce the level of Anxiety and fear among people

➤ *Hypothesis*

It is a prediction can be statistically tested and may be accepted or rejected Prediction about the relationship of Two or More variables

Null Hypothesis : In Which the calculated value is equal to given value

Alternative Hypothesis : In which the Calculated value is not equal to Given value

III. DISCUSSION

(S)= SIGNIFICANT & NOT SIGNIFICANT

df : Degrees of freedom

F : Frequency

% : Percentage

χ^2 : Chi square.

Fig 2 Reveals that 57.25 % of the participants had good level of ideas regarding Brain capability as compared to others and their Disorders. score regarding mentality and conditions among youth on various aspects like the Items related to health

Fig2 Knowledge Score

Fig 3 Reveal that 64.04% of the participants had positive attitude after Awareness and 62.79% participants had negative

Overall score of attitude is 63.67 .This shows that impact on our samples

Fig 3 Attitude Score

➤ *Impact*

- This program play a very vital role for upcoming generation
- Which is helpful their academic performance as well as in their life also
- It help to change the perspective of mind and break the barriers related new finding treatment and investigation
- Upbringings will be very curious about facts which is totally unknown
- Now a days people are so secure about our thinking and mind it will help them to give a proper definition about healthy life style

IV. CONCLUSION

- At the End we conclude that majorly most of the individuals know about the brain functioning or the positive and negative impact on brain due to psychological illness so we fundamental believe that human mindset total, changed due to awareness of various disorders
- Now world has many various option to treat in specialized department with trained doctors and nurses
- The Medical intervention and results are so effective due to care and updated technology in machines and medicines

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